

Application of GIS in Urban Solid Waste Management: A Case study in KCC

Kausik Das¹ and Sujit Kumar Sikder²

ABSTRACT

Urban solid waste management is considered as one of the most immediate and serious environmental problems confronting municipal authorities in developing countries like Bangladesh. A standard solid waste management should provide hygienic, efficient and economic collection, transportation and disposal of solid waste without polluting atmosphere. To ensure this standard management system GIS can be used as an effective tool in selecting suitable disposal sites and identifying the optimum routes for transportation. Suitable disposal sites and the optimum routes must have environmental safety criteria and attributes that will enable the wastes to be isolated so that there is no unacceptable risk to people or the environment while it is operating. The location of disposal sites of Khulna City Corporation represents the unconsciousness about the environmental and public health hazards. Response to this GIS here provides an opportunity to integrate spatial, aspatial data and other relevant data to select suitable disposal sites and identify optimum routes for transportation of solid waste. At this juncture GIS act as an important decision support system.

Key words:

Solid Waste, Geographic Information System (GIS), Disposal site, Spatial analysis, Routing.

BACKGROUND

With the innovations of new technology magnitude and severity of pollution is increasing. Most of the human activities lead to the generation of waste. Solid waste management, an indispensable part of our modern life, has become increasingly complicated science its earliest days. So it requires much attention to avoid environmental pollution. In Bangladesh urban solid waste generation is increasing proportionately with the growth of its population while solid waste management capacity of the cities and towns is lagging behind and the gap is widening everyday. All these are making the environmental scenarios of our urban life quite gloomy and dismal.

Generally in Bangladesh local government bodies are responsible for solid waste management and for which conservancy fee is charged on. Among them only major cities have some sort of disposal system where per capita production of solid waste is 0.5kg /day only 0.2 kg is carried to the final disposal (Farzana & Kabir, 2004). The rest is disposed off locally. This view of the major cities of any country obviously exhibits the poor waste management situation of that country. The disposal system of Khulna City is also not satisfactory at all. Not only the location of secondary disposal sites but also the transportation routes represent the unconsciousness about the environment and public health hazard. Because existing disposal sites and routes of waste transportation were not selected considering residential area, clinic/hospital, educational institution, drainage network, socio cultural institution etc. Suitable disposal sites and routes for transportation must have environmental safety criteria that will enable wastes to be isolated so that there would be no unacceptable risk to people and the environment while it will operate.

Selection of suitable sites for waste disposal has been normally carried by traditional approaches i.e. throwing it at all types of vacant land in or around the city. The Geographical Information System (GIS) can provide an opportunity to integrate field parameters with population and other relevant data or other associated features, which help in selection of sites. Site selection procedures can benefit from the appropriate use of GIS. The use of GIS in selection process will reduce the time and enhance the accuracy.

¹ Student, Master of Urban and Regional Planning Department, Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology (BUET), Dhaka, Bangladesh. Email: kausik_urb@yahoo.com

² Urban Planner/GIS Expert, Ministry of Local Government and Rural Development/EADS Ltd, Bangladesh, Email: sujiturp@yahoo.com

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- I. To find out potential secondary disposal sites for solid waste within KCC area using GIS.
- II. To identify the optimum route for transportation of solid waste collection and disposal.

SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this research is to introduce GIS as an effective decision support system which can also be useful in urban solid waste management. It can be used both in site selection phase for disposal and in optimum route identification for transportation. In the research selection criteria are imaginary as no standard is found for selecting suitable disposal site and transportation route.

STUDY AREA

Khulna is one of the divisional Cities of Bangladesh. It lies between 22° 49' north latitude and 89° 34' east longitudes and its elevation is 2.13 meters above mean sea level. City Corporation area of Khulna is 44.78 sq. km with population around 1.3 million. The Bhairab River and Fultala Thana bound Khulna on the north, by the Rupsha River on the east and south and on the west by Dumuria Thana. 71 percent of the households in KCC area have no fixed place for waste disposal. Total volume of solid waste generated in the study area is 411 ton per day. The present daily collection efficiency is only 23 % of the volume generated in the KCC area. The existing solid waste disposal site is situated in Rajbandh beside Khulna Satkhira road, about 8 km away from city centre. The total area of the present disposal site is only 12acres (*Environmental maps and workbook for Khulna City, 1999*). For improvement of solid waste management some new disposal sites are proposed in master plan.

GENERAL STEPS OF SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN THE STUDY AREA

Waste management in Khulna City area is mainly carried by KCC and the main source of finance for this is come from 6% of total collected municipal tax. (*Source: KCC Conservancy Department 2005*)

Generation: Total population of KCC area is 859906. And total about 400 ton waste is generated per day within KCC area. It is projected that the total waste will be 624 ton per day in the year 2010(*KDA & Aqua-Sheltech Consortium, 2002*).

Storage: On site storage for solid waste can be either individual or communal, using a portable and manually loadable container, a mechanically loadable container or concrete box fixed on a ground is present in the study area.

Collection: Different methods of solid waste collection from generation point by the concerned managing body are found in the study area. They are

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communal collection | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Curbside collection |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Block collection | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Door to door collection |

The present daily collection is only **23%** of the volume generated in KCC area. Beside these there are more than **1200 dustbins** (covered, open, ring, toe) located in different parts of the study area for smooth collection of sold waste.

Transportation: Waste from primary dustbin and other collection point of the disposal site are transported by various types of vehicle KCC has such as Sawraj Mazda, China dump truck, Hino truck, China truck, Hand cart & van etc. Total capacity of those vehicles is 126.38 ton (*Source: KCC Conservancy Department 2005*)

Disposal of solid waste: KCC uses only open dumping for disposal of wastes and sometimes wastes are sold to individual household to fill up a low land. At present only dumping site for KCC area is at Rajband, 3 km from Khulna University, about 8 km away from city centre and beside Khulna Satkhira road. The total area of the present disposal site is only 12acres (*Environmental maps*

and workbook for Khulna City, 1999). For improvement of solid waste management some new disposal sites are proposed in master plan. From the diagram it is clear that most of the household dispose their waste near by low land/ ditch located here and there. So it is prime work for KCC to locate some suitable disposal sites based on environmental safety criteria. In the entire solid waste management system of KCC, GIS can be used in two phase those are for identifying optimum transportation route and selection of suitable dumping sites.

Figure 2: Location final and secondary disposal sites

WORKING PROCEDURE OF THE RESEARCH

This particular research applied Constraint Mapping Technique to reduce the search area over vast land coverage and to leave only those areas that are suitable for waste disposal. The methodology of this research is presented below:

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|---|
| 1. Problem Identification | 2. Perform Spatial Operation |
| 3. Research Objective | 4. Analyze Results and |
| 5. Choose a Study Area | 6. Identification of Potential Search Area |
| 7. Decide on the Criteria | 8. Perform routing operation (network analysis) |
| 9. Acquire Data | 10. Identification of optimum route for transportation of solid waste |
| 11. Convert Criteria into GIS Layer | |

Figure 3: Flow chart of the methodology.

Steps 6, 7, 8 and 10 are the intelligent part where GIS operations take place. Step 9 provides one of the final results of this study, which is potential search area for solid waste disposal. And step 10 provides the least distance routes for transporting solid waste from different collection points and also from secondary disposal points to final disposal point at Rajbandh. It is pertinent to note that step 4 which is the input criteria plays a very important role at this phase of research because it can influence the result of the GIS operation.

Criteria development: To get environmental suitable potential area for solid waste disposal some general criteria have developed.

- Where should not be the disposal sites?
- Where should it be?

For example disposal sites should not be near of any settlement, school, health facilities, and should be near of drainage system or major roads for better accessibility.

Should not be criteria

- I. Site should not be within 1 km from any settlement
- II. Site should not be within 1 km from any health facilities
- III. Site should not be within 300 m from any water bodies
- IV. Site should not be within 500 m from any commercial establishment
- V. Site should not be within 500 m from any religious institutions

- VI. Site should not be within 750 m from any educational institutions
- ☑ **Should be criteria**
- VII. Site should be within 500 m from any dustbin
- VIII. Site should be within 300 m distant of any drain
- IX. Site should have better accessibility
- X. Should be in less densed area and Should be in low land
- XI. Area should be at least 6 acre (0.02428124 sq km)

After selecting the suitable dumping sites based on the criteria, the next job is to identify optimum waste collection routes from secondary points to the final disposal point. In this phase route analysis system would utilize to generate the most efficient routes that any vehicle can take. Network Analyst module enables users to solve a variety of problems using geographic networks such as finding the most efficient travel route, generating travel directions, finding the closest facility, or defining service areas based on travel time (Manoliadis and Vatalis, 2002). The routes would be developed using ARC/INFO's ARCEditW and ROUTEW modules in conjunction with a path finding algorithm within the NETWORK module. It is believed that, as ARC/INFO's spatial analyst becomes more widely used by municipalities, the NETWORK module is a tool that can be used to improve existing collection systems or to develop new ones.

Table 1: Sources of Data

Data List	Data Sources
Existing Land use Pattern	Structure plan, Master plan and Detailed area plan for Khulna City,2001
Population Information	
Land and Soil information	Soil Research Institute, Khulna
Commercial and Socio-Cultural establishment	Environmental Mapping & Work Book for Khulna City,1999
Existing road network and drainage system	
Location of dustbins and water bodies	
Existing Waste Disposal information	Conservancy Department of KCC

Data Flow Diagram (DFD)

Figure 4: Procedure of finding out potential sites for disposal

First of all buffer operations are used according to the criteria. Then 300m buffer of drain and 500m buffer of dustbin are combined together to get suitable areas. In the same method unsuitable areas are identified. Then from the suitable areas unsuitable areas are removed with spatial analysis operation (Geo Processing Wizard) of ARC GIS 9. After getting some possible sites, these would be evaluated according to the following criteria. In this phase “Selection By Attribute” and “Selection By Location” operation is used.

- I. Area should be at least 6 acre (0.02428124 sq km)
- II. Site should have better accessibility
- III. Should be in low densed area and be in low land

After the evaluation best sites for secondary disposal are identified. Probable sites are shown in flowing figure.

Figure 5: Possible sites for secondary disposal

Figure 6: Population density, Accessibility and Land elevation condition of suitable locations (Screen out)

Probable sites are then subject to rapid preliminary screening to narrow down numbers to more desirable sites. Potential search sites are found to be scattered in 8 different locations and also area of each sites is found more than 6 acre. “Selection By Attribute” operation of ARC GIS 9 is used for this screening. So all the eight scattered site are suitable according to total land area. But it is necessary to rank the areas to get the most preferable area for secondary disposal.

Table 2: Evaluation of suitable sites

Site no	Accessibility	Population density	Land elevation	Score
Site 1	1	1	1	3
Site 2	1	1	1	3
Site 3	1	0	1	2
Site 4	1	0	0	1
Site 5	0	0	0	0
Site 6	0	0	0	0
Site 7	0	1	1	2
Site 8	1	1	1	3

Accessibility: Here 1 = yes, 0 = no

Population density: In this study it is considered that below 10000 populations per sq kilometer is low densed area. Here 1 = low, 0 = high

Land elevation: In this study it is considered that below 3.5 m from MSL (mean sea level) land is low land. Here also 1 = low, 0 = high

Above screen out procedure is performed to identify most suitable secondary disposal using “Section By Location” operation of ARC GIS 9. After that total score of the eight sites are calculated manually. Based on the score 1, 2 and 8 number sites are selected. So these three are the most suitable locations for secondary waste disposal according to the criteria.

Figure 7: Procedure of identifying the optimum route for transportation

CONCLUSION

Suitable disposal sites and optimum transportation routes for solid waste demand comprehensive analysis and sound judgment. These processes often take longer to achieve but with the introduction of appropriate tools, decision making can be made faster and more reliable (Farzana & Kabir, 2004). The study findings provide evidence to the previous statement where GIS is used an effective, faster and reliable decision support system to identify possible areas for secondary disposal and optimum routes among these sites. Though GIS based methodology is highly sophisticated and standard but its success depend on the proper and careful application of it. In the research at first the total area was eliminated by applying constraint then leaving the balance of the potential search area. The remain 8 searched areas were then further screened out and finally 1, 2 and 8 no. sites are found as most suitable for secondary disposal. Then optimum route was selected amongst different accessible roads. Distance (in ft) & turn (in degree) are taken as impedance value to identify optimum route for transportation of solid waste in this study. But there are many other such criteria that could be included such as distance from residential area, school and surface of the road, vehicle type etc. Thus with the use of these technologies not only KCC but also other municipalities may manage its solid waste properly. And then it will no longer be a problem for city administrators. So GIS as decision support tools for managing solid waste has been proven to be useful.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, Feroze. and Rhaman, Majibur. (2003). *Water Supply and Sanitation*, ITN Bangladesh, centre for water supply and waste management, civil engineering building, BUET. pp 257-277.
- Cargin, Jeff and Dwyer, John. (1988). *Pennsylvania's Low-level Radioactive Waste disposal Facility Siting Project: Process Summary*, ESRI Conference Paper, ESRI.
- Farzana, F. and Kabir M.A. (2004). *Development of an Integrated GIS Based Methodology for the Selection of Solid Waste Disposal Sites for Khulna City*. Khulna University Studies 4(2); Khulna. pp 725 – 731.
- USAID. and Urban and Rural Planning Discipline, Khulna University. (1999). *Environmental Mapping and Work Book for Khulna City*.
- KDA. & Aqua-Sheltech Consortium. (2002). *Structure Plan, Master Plan and Detailed Area Plan for Khulna City*. Vol. iii, pp 111.
- Manoliadis, O. and Vatalis, K. (2002). *A two-level multi criteria DSS for Landfill Site Selection Using GIS: Case Study in Western Macedonia, Greece*. *Journal of Geographic Information and Decision Analysis*, Vol. 6, No. 1, pp 49-56.
- School of Social Sciences. (2003). *GIS as Decision Support Tool for Landfills Siting Gaim James Lunkapis*, University of Malaysia Sabah, Locked Bed 2073, 88999 Kota Kinabalu, Sabah, Malaysia.
- Access on: <http://www.esri.com/library/userconf/proc99/proceed/papers/pap464/p464.htm>